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Additional file 1: Figure S1. Principle and protocol of the AlphaLISA technique. In **A** Streptavidin-coated Donor-beads are bound to biotinylated antibodies. Acceptor-beads are directly coupled to antibodies. When both antibodies bind to an analyte, the beads are brought into close proximity. Donor-beads are excited at 680nm and produce singlet oxygen molecules triggering a chemical reaction in the close-by Europium Acceptor-beads resulting in an emission of light at 615nm. In **B** the protocol of a no-wash AlphaLISA is depicted.